

Digital Storytelling and Students' Academic Engagement in Civic Education: Implications for Sustainable Development

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Abstract

Background: The place of effective instructional delivery using appropriate innovative instructional delivery strategy is so pivotal in the teaching-learning process in this present age. Applying an instructional delivery strategy that is both effective and innovative in teaching a very important subject like Civic Education will no doubt contribute greatly to the attainment of quality education for all.

Objective: This research investigated the influence of digital storytelling on students' academic engagement in Civic Education, including gender as a moderating variable.

Methodology: The research used a quasi-experimental 2 x 2 factorial design. The research population comprised 2,684 senior secondary two (SSII) students, with 1,259 males and 1,425 females from 38 secondary schools in the Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State, Nigeria. This research used a sample of 183 students, including 85 males and 98 females, selected by purposive and simple random selection methods. The Academic Engagement Inventory (AEI) was used for data collection. The AEI received validation from specialists and exhibited a Cronbach's Alpha reliability value of .82 before administration, marking, scoring, and coding for analysis. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was utilized to evaluate the null hypotheses at a significance level of .05.

Results: Findings revealed a substantial disparity between the average academic engagement scores of secondary school pupils instructed in Civic Education using digital storytelling and those taught using traditional storytelling methods. Gender has no substantial effect on students' academic participation in Civic Education.

Conclusion: From the outcome, the conclusion is that digital storytelling instructional strategy positively influences academic engagement of students more than the traditional storytelling strategy irrespective of their gender.

Unique Contribution: This study enhances the existing knowledge base by demonstrating that the utilization of digital storytelling as a teaching strategy significantly improves students' academic engagement in Civic Education regardless of learner gender.

Keywords: Academic engagement, digital storytelling, civic education, instructional strategy, students, sustainable development.

Introduction

Digital storytelling holds a very inevitable place in the effective dissemination of learning instructions and materials in this age. It has emerged as an indispensable instrument in present-day education as it offers a captivating way to engage students with a view to enhancing their understanding, besides improving the delivery of subject matter (Bouchrika, 2025). Applying multimedia rudiments like text, images, audio and video in digital storytelling elicits unforgettable experiences that constantly echo in learners' minds, thus creating memories that result in desirable learning outcomes (Staley & Freeman, 2017; Johnson et al., 2024). Research indicates that multimedia educational packages, such as digital storytelling, significantly enhance the achievement of instructional goals and objectives compared to conventional teaching methods (Kurtz, 2015). This is because learning with such an innovative instructional package effectively controls the entire learning process, besides eliciting high student engagement and improved learning outcomes.

Digital storytelling is a personal narration that concurrently uses voice, imagery, and written text to convey a narrative (Staley & Freeman, 2017). It involves the creation of short story movies. Smeda et al. (2014) define it as an innovative instructional strategy that combines digital media to engage students effectively and efficiently in deep and meaningful learning. These scholars further see digital storytelling as a methodology integrating several technologies to augment and elevate textual or spoken narratives. Staley and Freeman (2017) define digital storytelling as an educational method that utilises computer-based resources to narrate tales by integrating audio, visuals, voice, text, and video.

Unlike the traditional media of storytelling that uses physical media materials (relics) such as paper posters and drawings on the board, a digital story uses materials that exist in electronic files (Bouchrika, 2025). These media may consist of brief combinations of text, photos, videos, or music that complement the recorded audio narration on subjects such as personal accounts, historical documentaries, or specific concepts and practices. Nkanu et al. (2024) assert that several topics within the Civic Education curriculum might be enhanced by means of new approaches, such as digital storytelling, to maintain student engagement for optimal learning outcomes. Innovative educational practices have been shown to stimulate critical thinking in students and enhance their engagement to connect with learning materials, as opposed to adopting a passive role in a teacher-centred classroom (Serdyukov, 2017). Nkanu et al. (2024) allude that the absence of a practical student-centred approach may have rendered students inactive and only to memorise to achieve high grades in examinations without the commensurate behavioural change in mindset and moral standard expected of them to be good ambassadors of their schools and communities. Given the invaluable place of Civic Education in the Nigerian school system, the need to employ innovative teaching methods in instructional delivery of its contents to students to achieve the objectives it is set out for becomes very inevitable. Notwithstanding the seemingly high potential of digital storytelling to improve students' engagement and achievement, as acknowledged by research (Nkanu et al., 2024; Johnson et al., 2025), there is a dearth of research on its utilisation in the present area of study and using Civic Education. Hence, the need for this study.

Being a compulsory subject, Adedigba (2019) avers that every student from senior secondary school is expected to have gone through the content of Civic Education. Scholars have diverged

in their definitions of civic education. It is the cornerstone of national value, coexistence, and identity in Nigeria. Balogun and Yusuf (2019) view it as a discipline aimed at achieving various objectives, including disseminating knowledge and instilling and cultivating essential values and belief systems, thus promoting productive engagements in matters of societal significance.

Numerous beneficial causes exist for instructing Civic Education in high schools. The objectives as delineated by the Nigerian Educational Research Development Council (NERDC) in 2009, encompass: fostering comprehension of the interrelationship among persons, government, and society; clarifying the government's organisation, operations, and the mutual responsibilities of people and the government; enhancing the teaching of current topics; and fostering in pupils a sense of their social responsibilities. Babo (2018) asserts that effective implementation of Civic Education objectives will produce responsible and law-abiding citizens, and assist young individuals in acquiring loyalty, integrity, discipline, courage, commitment, obedience, respect, nationalism, and diligence.

Teaching strategies are a very important factor in any instructional content delivery process. Civic Education curriculum developers advocate for engaging strategies such as storytelling, role play, inquiry, and dramatisation, along with other pertinent methods (NERDC, 2009). The publication underscored the need to integrate teaching and learning resources, including posters, pictures, video clips, diagrams, and artefacts, into the instruction of the Civic Education subject in Nigerian secondary schools to augment student learning. This study aimed to examine the effect of digital storytelling on students' academic engagement in civic education.

Research Hypotheses

Two null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the mean academic engagement scores of students taught Civic Education with digital and conventional storytelling strategies.

Ho2: There is no significant influence of gender on students' mean academic engagement scores in Civic Education.

Literature Review

This research examined several existing efforts on digital storytelling and student involvement. Ivala et al. (2013) explore the possibility of digital storytelling to improve student engagement in their academic pursuits. The study revealed that creating digital tales improved students' engagement with their studies, resulting in increased reflection and a deeper assimilation of the subject matter. Niemi et al. (2018) indicate that the DST technique directed students towards active collaborative learning, enabling them to acquire knowledge in mathematics and its application in daily life. The authors also reveal that DST promotes the utilization of innovative technologies in student learning and fosters the advancement of mathematical literacy and twenty-first-century skills. Russell-Atkinson (2013) investigates the effect of digital storytelling on the cognitive engagement of Grade 6/7 learners in language arts classrooms. The professor said that intellectual engagement was heightened due to digital storytelling. Rohayati (2020) conducted a study on the engagement of senior high school students in Indonesia with a genre-based digital storytelling project. Research revealed that digital storytelling markedly improved student participation in the project, especially in the selection of photographs and collaborative idea generation for the narrative. Karki et al. (2020) investigate engagement between college learners in metropolitan

Bangalore to examine institutional and individual academic engagement drivers. The authors discovered that 1. Substantial disparities in academic involvement existed across different courses/classrooms and years of study due to institutional factors. 2. Academic engagement among student-level factors shows substantial differences across genders and students' chosen majors. 3. Gender was correlated with involvement, with males demonstrating somewhat greater levels of engagement.

Students' gender may affect their academic involvement when using digital storytelling as an educational method. Amir et al. (2014) examine student involvement by age and gender via cross-sectional research conducted in Malaysia. The study results revealed that the amount of participation in school varies by age and gender. Junior pupils exhibited elevated levels of school involvement compared to their senior counterparts. Female students had a greater degree of involvement in comparison to male pupils. This indicates that the educational environment is experienced variably across various age groups and genders. Olayinka et al. (2021) examine the impact of gender on student involvement in social media at Taraba State University, Jalingo, Taraba, Nigeria. The researchers discovered a little impact of gender on student interaction with social media at Taraba State University.

From the foregoing review, especially as it concerns the moderating role of gender on digital storytelling and students' academic engagement in Civic Education, it can be inferred, to the best of the researchers' knowledge, that there is an apparent dearth of literature both in Civic Education and the location of this present study. This is one of the areas this study seeks to address.

Conceptual Model

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

The independent variable (Digital storytelling) as an instructional approach may directly influence students' academic engagement in Civic Education. Gender may have a main and moderating effect on students' engagement in Civic Education.

Research Method

Ethical Considerations

First, the researchers got approval from the departmental research ethics committee to carry out the study. Permission was also obtained from the school's head through a letter from the Head of the Department of Educational Technology, University of Calabar. The school's head also approved the informed consent forms that were given to the participating students. After explaining the purpose of the study, the researchers promised them anonymity of data.

Design and Sampling Procedure

This research adopted a quasi-experimental design. Specifically, the design is pretest-posttest non-equivalent control factorial research. Intact classes were used in the study. The study population comprised 2,684 senior secondary two (SSII) students of the 2023/2024 session, with 1,259 males

and 1,425 females, drawn from 38 secondary schools within the Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State, Nigeria. The study sample consists of 183 students, 85 males and 98 females, selected from two co-educational secondary schools using purposive and simple random selection methods. The choice of SSII students was due to the premises: that the themes to be treated for the study are in SS two curriculum, that they have been exposed to some pre-requisite knowledge of Civic Education concepts at SSI, and those within these age range tend to be most susceptible to peer pressure while, those in SSIII were preparing for external examination and may not have sufficient time for the study. The inclusion requirements were that the institution must be co-educational and possess facilities that effectively facilitate the transmission of audio-visual educational material accessible to students. A simple random sample procedure was used to pick two schools from the 11 that satisfied the aforementioned criteria for inclusion in the research. This was accomplished by sampling without replacement. To choose the two schools using simple random selection, the names of the 11 schools were inscribed on individual pieces of paper, which were then folded into a container and thoroughly mixed. The researcher randomly picked one school at a time from the container without replacement. The rationale for using the basic random sampling procedure was to ensure that each school had an equal opportunity to be chosen for the research. Simple random sampling was employed to assign classes from the two schools into experimental and control groups.

Instrumentation

The researchers adapted the Academic Engagement Inventory (AEI). The Academic Engagement Inventory (AEI) was adapted from Attention, Relevance, Confidence, Satisfaction (ARC'S) model of motivation by Keller (2012) to check students' engagement level in Civic Education. The instrument consisted of sections A and B. A collected demographic data from the students, while B was a 20-item four-point rating scale with options of Very High (VH), High (H), Low (L), and Very Low (VL). The experimental group was taught with the digital storytelling instructional strategy, while the control group was taught using the conventional storytelling strategy for four weeks.

Development of Digital Storytelling Instructional Intervention

The digital storytelling instructional strategy was designed and developed by the researchers in line with the lesson plan on the topics of drug use and abuse, the effects of drugs and drug abuse, prevention of drug abuse, and drug trafficking. The design and production followed the digital storytelling storyboard, using the multimedia technique. The need for the researcher-produced digital storytelling instructional intervention was anchored on the fact that digital storytelling is not currently used in the affected topics in Civic Education.

The researchers lined up different images, text, and short video clips of drugs and the dangers of drug abuse and trafficking in the computer system timeline using a software called Adobe Premiere Pro Version 2020 to produce the digital storytelling. First, the researchers recorded audio narrations using a voice recorder and playback for editing. Upon perfecting the audio, it was imported to the Adobe Premiere Pro software timeline and synchronized with the images, text, video, and characters. The final design was previewed and exported on MP4 format for instructional use. The exported packages were used to teach the experimental group as a digital storytelling intervention through multimedia projectors in the classroom, while the control group was taught with a conventional storytelling strategy using the lesson notes and instructional

materials for four weeks. The study utilises the normal class time and period, which is two classes per week and 40 minutes per session.

Validation

The (AEI) and the researchers made digital storytelling instructional packages were validated by five experts, one from the Department of Educational Foundation (Educational Psychology unit), one from the Department of Educational Management (Measurement and Evaluation unit), and three from the Department of Educational Technology, all in the University of Calabar. The internal consistency of AEI was evaluated through Cronbach’s Alpha. The dependability index was .82. The instrument was administered during the pre-test before and during the post-test, with items rearranged, following the treatment. The treatment was done by the Civic Education teachers from the sampled schools, who were trained as research assistants on how to teach using the digital storytelling instructional package, while the researchers supervised the process. The data was organised, labelled, evaluated, encoded, and analysed using IBM’s Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 23. Mean and Standard Deviation were employed to address the study issues, while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was utilised to assess all hypotheses at a significance level of 0.05.

Results

The result of the study is presented thus:

HO₁: No significant difference exists in the mean academic engagement scores of senior secondary school students taught Civic Education with digital storytelling and conventional storytelling strategy.

Table 1: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA)

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared (η^2_p)	Dec.
Corrected Model	14764.447 ^a	4	3691.112	69.291	.000	.609	
Intercept	17150.881	1	17150.88	321.963	.000	.644	
Pre-Academic Engagement Group	348.402	1	348.402	6.540	.011	.035	
Gender	12.140	1	12.140	.228	.634	.001	NS
Group * Gender	13.932	1	13.932	.262	.610	.002	NS
Error	9482.023	178	53.270				
Total	470220.000	183					
Corrected Total	24246.470	182					

The findings in Table 1 indicate a substantial disparity in the mean academic engagement scores of the experimental group and the control group, $F(1, 178) = 267.788$, $p = .000$, $\eta^2_p = .601$. The related probability (Sig.) value of .000 is below the 0.05 significance threshold at which the hypothesis was tested. Consequently, the first null hypothesis (HO₁), which posited that there is

no significant difference in the mean academic engagement scores of students instructed in Civic Education using digital storytelling compared to traditional storytelling strategies, is rejected. The effect size difference ($\eta^2p = .601$) shows that 60.1% of the variation exists between the mean academic engagement ratings of the experimental and control groups. There exists a significant disparity between the impacts of digital storytelling and traditional storytelling methods on the average academic engagement scores of senior secondary school pupils in Civic Education. The finding is a notable disparity in the mean academic engagement scores of school pupils instructed in Civic Education using digital storytelling compared to those taught using traditional storytelling methods.

Hypothesis Two

HO₂: There is no significant influence of gender on the mean engagement scores of students in Civic Education.

Table 2 presents the ANCOVA study on the impact of gender on the average engagement scores of students in Civic Education. This finding indicates that gender does not significantly affect the average academic engagement scores of students in Civic Education, $F(1, 178) = .228$, $p = .634$, $\eta^2p = .001$. This is because the related probability (Sig.) value of .634 exceeds the 0.05 threshold of significance at which the outcome is evaluated. Consequently, the second hypothesis (HO₂), which posits that gender does not significantly affect the mean academic engagement scores of senior secondary school students in Civic Education, is not rejected. Consequently, the conclusion is that gender does not significantly affect the mean academic engagement scores of senior secondary school students in Civic Education. This indicates that gender does not significantly affect the academic participation of secondary school pupils in Civic Education.

Discussion of Findings

The study's discoveries showed that students instructed in Civic Education using digital storytelling strategies exhibited greater mean academic engagement ratings compared to those taught via traditional storytelling methods. Subsequent findings indicated a substantial disparity in the average academic engagement scores of secondary school pupils instructed in Civic Education using digital storytelling compared to those taught using traditional storytelling methods. This indicates that the digital storytelling technique significantly enhances academic engagement among students in civic education compared to the traditional storytelling strategy.

The study's finding indicates that digital storytelling positively influences students' academic engagement more than conventional storytelling. It is likely due to its integration of digital media, which enhances students' involvement in learning activities for profound, effective, and meaningful education. It may be accurate since it aligns with the results of some prior investigations. This conclusion aligns with the results of Ivala et al. (2013), who indicated that digital storytelling improved student involvement, resulting in heightened reflection and comprehension of the subject matter. Similarly, the study supports Niemi et al. (2018), who demonstrated that digital storytelling facilitated active collaborative learning among students. Furthermore, the research corroborates the results of Rohayati's (2020) study, which indicated that digital storytelling significantly improved student involvement in learning activities, particularly in the selection of pictures and collaborative idea generation for the narrative. This suggests that digital storytelling may enhance students' academic engagement in Civic Education.

Digital storytelling effectively maintains learners' academic engagement by synthesising audio, images, voice, text, and video media. These enhancements bolster students' self-confidence, curiosity, and enthusiasm for collaborative engagement with peers, creating a significant learning experience that integrates media to enrich and elevate both written and spoken communication (Niemi et al., 2018). This differs from traditional storytelling, which uses tangible media such as paper posters and whiteboard drawings; a digital tale utilises elements stored in computer files (Bouchrika, 2025). Consequently, students instructed in Civic Education by digital storytelling strategies may get greater mean academic engagement ratings compared to those taught via traditional storytelling methods.

The study's findings showed that both male and female students exhibit a high level of academic engagement in Civic Education; however, male students demonstrated a marginally greater engagement improvement than their female counterparts. It was further shown that gender does not significantly affect the average academic engagement scores of secondary school pupils in Civic Education. This indicates that gender does not significantly influence students' academic involvement. Both male and female students have enhanced their academic commitment.

The aforementioned finding corroborates the research conducted by Olayinka et al. (2021), which examined the impact of gender on students' engagement with social media at Taraba State University in Jalingo, Nigeria, and concluded that gender does not significantly affect students' social media engagement at this institution. Karki et al. (2020) examined academic involvement among college students in metropolitan Bangalore and discovered a correlation between gender and engagement, with males demonstrating somewhat greater levels of engagement. Nonetheless, this study contradicts Amir et al. (2014), who demonstrated that school involvement levels vary by gender, with female pupils exhibiting more engagement than their male counterparts. This conclusion is unexpected, since one would anticipate a significant disparity in self-efficacy between male and female students, given the prevalent belief that male students often excel in Civic Education compared to their female peers. The results may be valid owing to other school-related variables.

Conclusions

This research found that the digital storytelling instructional technique positively influences academic engagement in Civic Education among senior secondary school students more than the traditional storytelling strategy. Consequently, civic education instructors who adopt a digital storytelling technique will have more favourable outcomes in boosting students' academic engagement and self-efficacy than traditional storytelling methods. Gender does not significantly affect students' academic involvement in Civic Education. Therefore, the digital storytelling teaching technique successfully enhances students' academic engagement in Civic Education.

Recommendations

This research yielded the following recommendations:

1. students should be directed to engage energetically in learning activities that use digital storytelling strategies, since they have the potential to enhance their creative and critical thinking skills.

2. civic education instructors should be motivated to use the digital storytelling technique to augment students' academic engagement in Civic Education.
3. the government, via the ministries of education, should facilitate seminars and workshops for Civic Education instructors on the use of digital storytelling strategies in the pedagogy of the subject.
4. both male and female students should be encourage to engage fully in learning activities that use digital storytelling strategies, since they have shown effectiveness for both genders.
5. Additional research should be conducted on the impact of digital storytelling as an instructional technique in additional social science education courses to validate its usefulness.

Implications for Sustainable Development

The study's results indicated that students instructed in civic education through digital storytelling had superior mean academic engagement scores compared to those taught via traditional storytelling methods. This result has invaluable implications for sustainable development, particularly quality education, as highlighted by SDG 4. Quality education that will birth lifelong opportunities in all walks of life is achievable through effective delivery of instructional content in the teaching-learning environment using innovative instructional delivery strategies like digital storytelling. Where students become well acquainted with civic education content courtesy of being taught with a digital storytelling instructional strategy, high chances abound that they will grow up as responsible citizens who will contribute in no small measure towards building a sustainable democratic nation. Moreover, students will be thoroughly groomed to become disciplined and responsible citizens who will not be myopically inclined to using the nation's resources for the satisfaction of their immediate needs but will instead put them to use for their sustenance without compromising the chances of the upcoming generations meeting their own needs through these same resources. The findings of this study equally suggest that through an effective instructional process, students will acquire the right attitude, knowledge, morals, and basic skills that will motivate them to contribute to building a society that we shall all be proud to be identified with.

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